

Formation Constants of some Vanadyl Chelates

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The formation constants of the chelates of vanadyl ion with catechol, pyrogallol, protocatechuic acid and gallic acid have been determined at 35° by Calvin-Melchior and Irving-Rossotti techniques in order to bring out the relative merits of the two methods.

The phenols have been reported to form complexes with a number of metals. The formation of vanadyl catecholate and pyrogallolate of composition 1 : 2 and 1 : 1, respectively, has been reported¹⁻⁴. The complex formation of gallic acid with vanadyl ion has been studied spectrophotometrically. No systematic determination of the stability constants of VO⁺⁺ complexes with phenols and phenolic acids has been done and hence the present investigation has been undertaken.

Catechol, pyrogallol, protocatechuic acid, gallic acid, vanadyl chloride, sodium perchlorate, perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide were of A.R. quality.

Metrohm pH meter Model E 350 A was used which reads upto an accuracy of ± 0.05 . A constant temperature bath was used to maintain constant temperature with an uncertainty of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Determination of stability constants : The stepwise formation constants were determined by Calvin-Melchior⁵ and Irving-Rossotti⁶ techniques. The solutions containing perchloric acid, perchloric acid+ligand and perchloric acid+ligand+metal solution each diluted to a constant volume (50 ml.) with conductivity water and maintained at constant ionic strength (0.2M) by the addition of neutral salt NaClO₄ were titrated against standard alkali. Nitrogen was bubbled through the solution during the titration. In all, thus three titrations were performed. Curves were obtained by plotting pH against the volume of alkali. From these titrations curves \bar{n} and pL were obtained by Calvin-Melchior and Irving-Rossotti methods as given in the following tables. \bar{n} and pL values have an accuracy of ± 0.2 and $\pm .05$ respectively. The K_1 and K_2 values have been worked out by the least square treatment. The values have an accuracy of $\pm .05$.

According to Calvin-Melchior method the liberation of two hydrogen ions per ligand molecule takes place as a result of the complex formation. Thus the method considers that these hydrogen atoms remain completely undissociated from the ligand at that pH in the absence of the complex formation.

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TABLE 1

V^{o++}—Catechol 35°

B	V'''—V''	V''	\bar{n}		pL	
			(CM)	(IR)	(CM)	(IR)
3.5	0.210	2.45	0.42	0.4225	17.682	16.980
3.6	0.270	2.47	0.54	0.5431	17.488	16.789
3.7	0.335	2.485	0.67	0.6712	17.342	16.603
3.8	0.400	2.500	0.80	0.803	17.103	16.405
4.0	0.490	2.520	0.98	0.9818	16.711	16.010
4.2	0.575	2.533	1.15	1.1512	16.362	16.412
4.5	0.675	2.545	1.35	1.3497	15.731	15.031
4.7	0.750	2.548	1.50	1.4988	15.249	15.640
5.0	0.827	2.553	1.654	1.6534	14.748	14.048
5.5	0.876	2.558	1.752	1.727	17.753	13.700
6.0	0.891	2.567	1.782	1.7828	12.755	13.108
6.5	0.914	2.576	1.828	1.9192	11.758	11.712
7.0	1.003	2.587	2.006	2.0129	10.768	

In the Irving-Rossotti technique, however, an additional term $\bar{n}A$ is introduced which indicates the average number of the hydrogen ions bound per not complex bound ligand.

$$\bar{n}A = YTL^\circ + \frac{(V' - V'')(N + E^\circ)}{(V^\circ + V')} \Big/ TL^\circ$$

where Y is the number of replaceable hydrogens. Catechol has two replaceable hydrogens. Since $\bar{n}A$ value does not go below one for pyrogallol, protocatechuic acid and gallic acid even at a very high pH and the ligands are bidentate it is assumed that only two hydrogen ions are being released per ligand molecule. Hence Y has been considered two for them also. \bar{n} and pL were calculated by the following equations.

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'')N + E^\circ + TL^\circ (Y - \bar{n}A)}{(V^\circ + V'')\bar{n}A TM^\circ}$$

$$pL = \log \frac{1 + p_k h \left(\frac{1}{(\text{antilog } pH)} \right)}{TL^\circ - \bar{n} \cdot TM^\circ} \cdot \frac{V^\circ + V'''}{V^\circ}$$

The Irving-Rossotti method uses the $p_k H$, practical proton ligand stability constant. The $p_k H$ has been determined under experimental conditions from the relationship $\log p_k H = pH + \log \bar{n}A / (1 - \bar{n}A)$ at different points on the straight line obtained by the plot of pH against $\log \bar{n}A / (1 - \bar{n}A)$. The $p_{k_1} H$ value has been calculated by the relationship $\log p_{k_1} H - p_{k_2} H = 2pH$ at $\bar{n}A$ one.

TABLE 2

VO⁺⁺—Protocatechuic acid 35°

\bar{n}		pL	
CM	IR	CM	IR
0.560	0.470	12.10	11.41
0.580	0.590	11.90	11.22
0.600	0.620	11.70	11.02
0.980	1.000	11.09	10.45
1.120	1.210	10.730	10.10
1.200	1.370	10.52	9.83
1.300	1.490	10.14	9.57
1.420	1.650	10.06	9.37
1.520	1.780	9.76	9.25
1.600	2.280	8.77	8.38

The dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 used in Calvin-Melchior method for the calculation of pL values are the reciprocals of experimental proton ligand stability constants. No additional accuracy is, therefore, attained in the calculation of pL in the Irving-Rossotti method. There is however an improvement in the calculation of \bar{n} .

Irving-Rossotti method does not consider $\bar{n}A$ to be always equal to two and is therefore, more practical and gives better values of \bar{n} than the Calvin-Melchior method. Since \bar{n} calculations have been made at lower pH and the catechol and pyrogallol being weak acids have little dissociation at that pH . \bar{n} values at different pH by both the methods are almost same (Table 1). Slight difference in \bar{n} values starts at higher pH when there is some self dissociation of these ligands.

The \bar{n} values obtained by the two methods in the case of protocatechuic acid and gallic acid complexes with vanadyl ion differ significantly (Table 2). This is due to the sufficient self dissociation of the ligand at the pH where calculations are done. The values obtained by Irving-Rossotti method considering actual $\bar{n}A$ are more reliable. From the values of

\bar{n} and pL the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been calculated by the application of the least square method. The values worked out to be as follows :

TABLE 3

Vanadyl Complex	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Catecholate	16.85	14.63
Pyrogallolate	15.15	13.42
Protocatechuate	11.37	9.58
Gallate	9.00	7.47

Thanks are due to Prof. W. V. Bhagwat, Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain and Prof. S. M. Sethna, Head, Department of Chemistry, M.S. University of Baroda for providing laboratory facilities.

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Received February 3, 1969.